

Electromagnetic Waves from Gauss' Law and Special Relativity

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The photon is usually described by electromagnetic wave equations written for E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) separately for a no source situation, with $c = \text{speed of light in a vacuum} = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$.

Here, we argue that one may find an em wave structure by only considering Gauss' law and special relativity. In a previous note (1), we argued that one may find $c=1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$ from similar considerations.

Gauss' Law

$$\text{Gauss' law: } \text{grad dot } E = \text{charge density} \left[\frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \right] \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{leads to: } -\text{grad dot grad } \phi = \text{charge density} \left[\frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \right] \quad ((2))$$

for a point charge at rest at $r=0$, with charge density being: $Q \delta(r=0)$. This in turn leads to the solution:

$$\phi = \left[\frac{Q}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \right] \frac{1}{r} \quad \text{where } r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad ((3))$$

We next consider viewing this charge Q from a frame moving with constant $-v$. We note that $q \phi$ is potential energy and acts like a rest mass energy and so should transform like the fourth component of a 4-vector.

Under a Lorentz transformation, this leads to:

$$\phi = g \phi(r) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{momentum vector} = g v(x) \phi(r) \quad ((4)) \quad v(x) = \text{unit } x \text{ vector}$$

$$g = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

ϕ and the momentum vector should be described in terms of x, y, z not r so one may use the inverse Lorentz transformation:

$$X = x - vt, \quad y = y, \quad z = z \quad ((5))$$

Given that $-\text{grad } \phi$ is linked to E and, hence force in the rest frame, both ϕ and the momentum vector, after being acted on linearly by d/dt partial and grad , should also be linked to force. One must, however, find the exact details for this as done in (1). This leads to:

$$F = q E + q v \times B \quad ((6)) \quad \text{where } v \text{ is the velocity vector of a moving charge, } B = \text{grad } \times A$$

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial and } A = g (\mu_0 \epsilon_0) v \phi(x) \quad ((7))$$

It was noted in (1) that if one uses only $-\text{grad } \phi$ (in the moving frame) then one has the vector:

$$\text{grad } \phi = (x-vt) e(x) + y e(y) + z e(z) \quad ((8))$$

We argued in ((1)) that the vector seen in the moving frame should be $(x-vt) e(x) + y e(y) + z e(z)$ and showed that using: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ accomplishes this.

Here we note that in the moving frame:

$\text{grad } \cdot \text{grad } \phi$ is no longer charge density and so a modification to Gauss' Law is needed. We suggest that charge density transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. Then:

$$\phi \rightarrow \phi' = \gamma \phi \quad \text{and} \quad \rho \rightarrow \rho' = \gamma (\rho - v j) \quad ((9))$$

$r = \sqrt{(x-vt)^2 + y^2 + z^2}$ so:

$$-\text{grad } \cdot \text{grad } \phi = -\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left\{ \frac{-2}{r^{3/2}} + 3 \frac{(x-vt)(x-vt) + y^2 + z^2}{r^{5/2}} \right\} \quad ((10))$$

((10)) requires a term such that:

$$\frac{-2}{r^{3/2}} \left(\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \right) \rightarrow -\frac{3}{r^{3/2}} \left(\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \right) \quad ((11))$$

This may be accomplished by adding $-dA/dt$ to $-\text{grad } \phi$. Thus, one has an extra piece, using ((7))

$$\text{grad } \cdot (-dA/dt) = -v \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d\phi}{dx} \right) \quad ((12)) \quad \text{with } \epsilon_0 = 1/c^2$$

Combining with the x piece of $-\text{grad } \cdot \text{grad } \phi$ converts γ to 1 and one has the required 3 in the numerator.

$$\text{Then: } \left\{ \text{grad } \cdot \text{grad} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \right\} \phi = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \rho \quad ((12))$$

A similar equation should hold for A with charge density replaced with current density and $1/\epsilon_0$ with $1/c$. We note that this D'Alembertian form and the A D'Alembertian together with $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ and $B = \text{grad } \times A$ essentially constitute Maxwell's four EM equations and the Lorentz force.

The term in $\{\}$ is the D'Alembertian and is Lorentz invariant. The D'Alembertian, however, is of the form of a wave-equation. In the above, one has a delta function source on the RHS, but if there were no delta function source and 0 instead, one would have:

$$\left\{ \text{grad } \cdot \text{grad} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \right\} \phi = 0 \quad \text{and the same equation with } \phi \text{ replaced with } A. \quad ((13))$$

This leads to a math solution of $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ for ϕ , because motion is in the x direction. It is not clear, however, what to do with A in this case. For a charged particle, A is a vector in the direction of $e(x)$. If one retains that convention here, then

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad E=0 \text{ is not interesting. } ((14))$$

If, however, one considers $A = \{\exp(-i\omega t + ikx), \exp(-i\omega t + ikx), \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)\}$ and $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ then for $\omega/k=c$, using $c=1$ and dropping e_0 , u_0 here, one has:

$$E = (0, \exp(ikx - i\omega t), \exp(ikx - i\omega t)) \quad \text{and} \quad B = \{0, -k \exp(-i\omega t + ikx), k \exp(ikx - i\omega t)\}$$

B and E are orthogonal to each other and lie in a plane perpendicular to the direction of motion.

Thus, there is periodic motion of E and B in a plane perpendicular to motion with $c=1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$. This is obtained without officially using Maxwell's equations other than $\text{grad } \text{div } E = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{ charge density}$ and the $B = \text{grad } \times A$, $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial. We argued above for the latter and the former may also be deduced only from the Lorentz transformation. Thus, one does not need the full Maxwell equations to deduce the form of a light E - B wave, only special relativity and Gauss' law, we argue. Furthermore, these considerations essentially lead to Maxwell's four em equations and the Lorentz force.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that light as an em wave usually follows from two wave equations, one for E (electric field) and the other for B (magnetic field), with charge and current densities being set to zero. These are obtained from Maxwell's EM equations.

Here we consider Gauss' law for a charge at rest and Lorentz transform $q \phi$, where ϕ is the potential in the rest frame. We argue that $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial with $A = \epsilon_0 u_0$ transformed momentum $c = \epsilon_0 u_0 v g \phi$ ($g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$), allows for the D'Alembertian to equal $1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{ charge density}$ g , where charge density is a delta function. This is the generalization of $-\text{grad } \text{div } \phi = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{ charge density}$ from the rest frame.

The D'Alembertian may also be used on A , but current density appears on the RHS. We suggest that without sources, one may find solutions for A and ϕ , namely $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A = (\exp(-i\omega t + ikx) (1, 1, 1))$. This leads to E and B fields perpendicular to motion and to each other and periodic, i.e light. This follows only from special relativity and the Gauss' law, with $-\text{grad } \text{div}$ in the rest frame becoming the D'Alembertian and one seeking solutions with no sources.

Furthermore, these considerations essentially lead to Maxwell's four EM equations and the Lorentz force.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Finding the Speed of Light From Gauss' Law and Special Relativity (preprint, zenodo, 2024)

